

VOICE GUIDED SYSTEM USING NLP AND SPEECH RECOGNITION FOR MALAYALAM LANGUAGE

Diyamol Jacob
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
diyamoljacob2023a@mca.ajce.in

Merin Chacko
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
merinmanoj@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— This project aims to develop a Voice-Guided system (Voice Chat-Bot) that leverages the power of speech recognition and NLP technologies to enhance human-machine interaction. The system starts by recording the user's voice using a speech recognition library. As it is both voice and text based, it assists the user as a human assisting with their questions. It provides multiple interaction modes to accommodate users with different language preferences. Next, it utilizes the ALBERT-base-v2-squad_v2 model to analyze the user's input and generate an appropriate response. The SQuAD v2 model, a question-answering algorithm trained on a vast corpus of text data, was also used to construct the voice guided system. Then it translates the response generated by the system back into the user's language using NLP techniques, resulting in a seamless and natural conversation.

Keywords-Natural Language Processing, Speech Recognition, Chatbot, albert-base-v2-squad_v2 model, Pytorch.

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural Language processing (NLP), a quickly developing field, has appeared to offer critical potential for understanding issues within the genuine world. Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Speech Recognition have cleared the way for the creation of voice guided system (voice activated chat-bots), which might revolutionize customer interactions on any platform.

In recent time, the ubiquity of voice-activated chat-bots has expanded due to progressions in NLP and Speech Recognition. These chat-bots can be utilized for an assortment of purposes, such as client benefit, individual collaborators, and e-commerce. This paper centers on the potential of voice-based chat-bots to move forward the online rental platform experience for non-technical clients who may confront language barriers or trouble exploring websites and filling out forms. This system utilizes advanced NLP techniques and speech recognition libraries to enable natural language input and provide real-time responses to users. The user's voice is

first recorded using a speech recognition library. It also offers multiple modes of interaction to support different languages and the chat-bot then processes and responds to the user's queries using a pre-trained SQuAD v2 model. Finally, the response generated by the chat-bot is translated back into the user's preferred language using NLP translation techniques. By utilizing advanced NLP techniques and speech recognition libraries, the proposed chat-bot system offers a voice-guided system that helps users overcome these obstacles and makes the rental process more accessible and user-friendly. The paper's main objective is to showcase the potential of voice-activated chat-bots in transforming the rental platform industry, offering an individualized, comfortable, and user-friendly experience that reduces the time and effort required to search and purchase products online, benefiting both customers and enterprises or the potential to significantly transform the online rental platform industry by making it easier and more convenient for users to find and rent products, leading to greater customer satisfaction and loyalty. In conclusion, the chat-bot system is designed to improve the rental experience for users by translating their natural language input, providing accurate responses, and personalizing the conversation to the user's language preference. This approach seems revolutionize the online rental platform industry by improving client fulfillment, pulling in unused clients who already battled with language barriers, and making the rental platform more productive and user-friendly.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sagina Athikkal and John Jenq. [1], titled "Voice Chatbot for Hospitality", outlines the creation of a closed domain question-answering chatbot for the hospitality industry. The chatbot's purpose is to assist hospital guests by providing information and aid through natural language voice interactions. The authors explain how natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition technologies are used to enable the chatbot to comprehend and respond to

queries within the limited domain of hospitality. Additionally, a knowledge graph is utilized to provide personalized recommendations to patients based on their preferences and previous interactions. The paper concludes by evaluating the chatbot's effectiveness in the hospitality domain and highlighting future research directions.

Mr. P.V.M. Vijay Bhasker, Mr. K. Hari Krishna, Mrs. A. Sirisha, and Mr. V. Madhava Reddy. [2], In their paper "Chat Bot Design Using NLP and KNN Algorithm," explain how they designed and implemented a chatbot for use in customer service applications. They utilized Natural Language Processing(NLP) techniques and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm to extract features from client request and classify them to provide speedy and exact responses. The authors conducted tests to assess the performance of the chatbot and found that it accomplished high precision and performed well in classifying questions and answers. The study suggests that NLP and KNN algorithm can be used in chatbot design for customer service applications and also provides recommendations for further research, including the use of machine learning and deep learning techniques to enhance chatbot performance in complex environments.

Girish Palshikar, Pradnya Karbhari, and Gauri Joshi. [3], in their paper "Speech Recognition and Natural Language Processing Techniques for Voice-Activated Control of Home Automation Systems", in this paper they discuss how speech recognition and natural language processing techniques can be used to enable users to interact with home automation systems through voice-activated controls or spoken commands in their native tongue. Security, climate control, and lighting are just a few of the home automation elements that the system is designed to manage. The study examines the use of Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) for speech recognition and natural language processing techniques such as parsing, semantic analysis, and syntactic analysis to aid the system in understanding and carrying out user commands. The authors also discuss utilising a framework with rules for control and decision making.

Dr Raju Shanmugam, Mr. Soumya Ranjan Jena. [4], In their paper "College Information Chat-Bot System Based on Natural Language Processing", the paper proposes the development of a natural language processing (NLP)-based chat-bot system that aims to offer educational institution-related information to college students. Specifically, the system utilizes NLP algorithms to enable effective communication with the students. It expounds upon the operational framework of the system, which comprises the examination of user inquiries, the retrieval of pertinent data from a collegiate database, and the presentation of responses in a manner that is easily comprehensible to users. Also it acknowledges the challenges involved in the development of an effective system, wherein notable hurdles include the necessity for precise natural language processing algorithms and an all-inclusive database of collegiate information.

Aayush Doshi and Deep Vakharia. [5], The paper "Alexis: A Voice-based Chat-bot using Natural Language Processing" describes the creation of a chatbot that utilizes speech recognition and natural language processing to streamline user interactions within educational institutions. The authors

utilized Python language and the Common Dialect Toolkit (NLTK) to plan the chat-bot. They too utilized a range of algorithms and tools for speech recognition, nlp, and machine learning to improve the chat-bot performance and to automate and streamline user interactions in educational institutions. It can serve as a supportive asset for analysts and engineers interested about creating similar chat-bots.

III. MOTIVATION

In the contemporary era of technology, the interaction of individuals with machines has emerged as an indispensable element in our routine existence. The advent of voice assistants and chat-bots has engendered an escalating need for more streamlined and spontaneous modes of interaction with advanced technological systems. Consequently, a surge in demand is evident for the development of voice-activated systems that can proficiently employ the capabilities of speech recognition and natural language processing (NLP) technologies to enhance the interaction between humans and technological devices.

The integration of voice-guided systems with Natural Language Processing (NLP) and speech recognition technology holds considerable transformative potential for the way individuals engage with technology. The implementation of voice-guided systems, which facilitate communication between users and devices or applications through natural language, can significantly enhance accessibility and user-friendliness of technology and consequently augment user experience and satisfaction. Furthermore, employing natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition technology for automating the voice-guided system can result in time and resource savings, allowing for a systematic and automated analysis of voluminous user input.

The utilization of this approach has the potential to furnish a comprehensive and precise depiction of the users' attitudes and inclinations, thereby facilitating software developers to enhance the efficacy of their vocalized assistance technology and augment consumer contentment. The present seminar paper aims to present a thorough overview of the various potential applications and advantages of voice-guided systems that employ natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition technologies. Through the utilization of these technologies, software developers have the capability to design more user-friendly and perceptible applications, leading to heightened customer contentment and ultimately attaining heightened triumph within the present-day digital world.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The process of creating a Voice-Guided System entails a multifaceted approach as well as utilization of various technologies.

A. Record User's Voice: To capture vocal input from users, the utilization of the Speech Recognition module in Python is recommended.

```
import speech_recognition as sr

r = sr.Recognizer()
with sr.Microphone() as source:
    print("Speak now...")
    audio = r.record(source, duration=5)
text = r.recognize_google(audio)
print(text)
```

Fig1

B. Translate Malayalam Input to English: During this step, the user's input in Malayalam will be translated to English to enable processing by the natural language processing models. To achieve this objective, it is proposed to utilize the 'Googletrans' library, which is compatible with the Python programming language. Googletrans is a no-cost and boundless Python library which effectively integrates Google Translate API.

```
from googletrans import Translator
translator = Translator()
malayalam_text="ഹലോ, നിങ്ങളുടെ സുഖമാണോ?"
english_text = translator.translate(malayalam_text, dest='en').text
print(english_text)
```

Hello how are you?

Fig 2

C. Generate Response Using ALBERT-base-v2- squad_v2 Model: The ALBERT-base-v2-squad_v2 model is employed for analyzing user input and subsequently producing a suitable response rooted in the input's contextual framework. The state-of-the-art language model, ALBERT, has been developed by Google AI Language utilizing the technique of self-supervised learning for generating text representations. The model has undergone extensive training using a significant volume of data, enabling it to comprehend the contextual nuances of the input.

```
from transformers import AutoTokenizer, AutoModelForQuestionAnswering
import torch
tokenizer = AutoTokenizer.from_pretrained('squirro/albert-base-v2-squad_v2')
model = AutoModelForQuestionAnswering.from_pretrained('squirro/albert-base-v2-squad_v2')
```

Fig 3

The ALBERT model for question answering is trained on the SQuAD v2 dataset. The SQuAD v2 dataset comprises text passages together with corresponding questions and answers, and serves as a means of assessing the efficacy of question-answering models. Throughout its training period, the ALBERT model acquires the capability to prognosticate the response to a question provided, by taking into account the textual passage at hand.

```
inputs = tokenizer.encode_plus(question, context, add_special_tokens=True, return_tensors='pt')
input_ids = inputs["input_ids"].tolist()[0]
outputs = model(**inputs)
answer_start_scores = outputs.start_logits
answer_end_scores = outputs.end_logits
answer_start = torch.argmax(answer_start_scores)
answer_end = torch.argmax(answer_end_scores) + 1
answer = tokenizer.convert_tokens_to_string(tokenizer.convert_ids_to_tokens(input_ids[answer_start:answer_end]))
```

Fig 4

In the implemented voice-guided system, the ALBERT-base-v2-squad_v2 model is utilized for the purpose of analyzing the input of the user, which may be in the form of text or speech. The input is subjected to processing and tokenization, employing the same techniques utilized during the training phase. The aforementioned model subsequently elicits a reply predicated on the contextual framework of the input. The manner in which one may respond can manifest as either a written reply or an auditory output produced through the utilization of text-to-speech mechanisms.

The ALBERT-base-v2-squad_v2 model is a pre-trained model that can be seamlessly integrated into our voice-guided system through various established deep learning frameworks, including but not limited to PyTorch. The model may undergo further refinement by means of customization with proprietary dataset, or alternatively used in its existing state for the purpose of addressing queries.

In general, the utilization of the ALBERT-base-v2- squad_v2 model enhances the functionality of our voice- guided system by enabling it to comprehend users' input and produce relevant responses contingent upon the given context. This feature enhances the naturalness and seamlessness of the interaction with the system.

D. Translate Response: The response generated by the system is translated back into Malayalam using Googletrans. Googletrans is a Python library that uses the Google Translate API to perform translations between different languages.

After the response is generated by the ALBERT-base-v2-squad_v2 model, the response is in English. Since our voice-guided system is planned to be associated with clients who talk Malayalam, we have to interpret the response back into Malayalam for the user to understand it. To perform the translation, we utilize the Googletrans library, which permits us to call the Google Interpret API from within our Python code. We pass the English response created by the model as input to the library's translate() function, along with the source language (English) and target language (Malayalam) parameters.

The library then uses the Google Translate API to translate the response into Malayalam and returns the translated text as output. This interpreted content can at that point be displayed to the user through the front-end of the voice-guided system. Overall, this step makes a difference to

guarantee that our voice-guided system can successfully communicate with clients who incline toward to utilize Malayalam as their primary language, making it more open and user-friendly.

Fig:5

IV. CONCLUSION

The creation of a Voice-Guided system, incorporating speech recognition and natural language processing technologies, exhibits the ability to significantly transform the way humans interact with machines. This study presents a system that capitalizes on the proficiency of speech recognition via the employment of the Speech Recognition module, as well as natural language processing by utilizing the ALBERT-base-v2-squad_v2 model and SQuAD v2 dataset. The system demonstrates proficiency in analyzing user input and producing a pertinent response on the basis of context, thereby enabling it to serve as an efficacious instrument for addressing queries and directing users. Furthermore, the system facilitates diverse interaction modes to cater to users with distinct language preferences, (Malayalam) employing Googletrans for translations. The system that has been created, guided by voice, has the potential to essentially upgrade the effectiveness and accessibility associated with interactions between humans and machines.

V. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of a voice-guided system using NLP and speech recognition is vast and promising. With the increasing demand for automation and ease of access, such systems have

the potential to be widely adopted in various fields. As technology advances, the accuracy and reliability of speech recognition and NLP are also expected to improve. This will lead to more efficient and seamless voice-guided systems that can perform complex tasks with ease. Additionally, with the growing popularity of smart homes and the Internet of Things (IoT), voice-guided systems can also be integrated with home automation to create a more convenient and comfortable living experience. Overall, the future of voice-guided systems using NLP and speech recognition is exciting and full of potential for various industries and everyday life.

VI .REFERENCES

- [1] Athikkal, Sagina & Jenq, John. (2022). Voice Chatbot for Hospitality. 10.48550/arXiv.2208.10926.
- [2] Mr. P.V.M. Vijay Bhasker, Mr. K. Hari Krishna, Mrs. A. Sirisha, & Mr. V. Madhava Reddy. 1 June, 2021.
- [3] Girish Palshikar, Pradnya Karbhari, and Gauri Joshi. "Speech Recognition and Natural Language Processing Techniques for Voice-Activated Control of Home Automation Systems" sep 2021.
- [4] Shanmugam, Dr Raju & Jena, Mr. Soumya & Gaur, Vishvaketan. (2020). College Information Chat-Bot System Based on Natural Language Processing. Xi'an Dianzi Keji Daxue Xuebao/Journal of Xidian University. 14. 825-831. 10.37896/jxu14.5/086.
- [5] Doshi, Aayush & Papat, Meet & Vakharia, Deep & Rai, Yashraj & Tusciano, Grinal. (2022). Alexis : A Voicebased Chatbot using Natural Language Processing.
- [6] Withanage, Pooja, et al. "Voice-based road navigation system using natural language processing (nlp)." 2018 IEEE International Conference on Information and Automation for Sustainability (ICIAfS). IEEE, 2018.
- [7] Du Preez, Salomon Jakobus, Manoj Lall, and Saurabh Sinha. "An intelligent web-based voice chat bot." IEEE EUROCON 2009. IEEE, 2009.
- [8] Kadali, Bhavyasri, et al. "Home automation using chatbot and voice assistant." ITM Web of Conferences. Vol. 32. EDP Sciences, 2020.
- [9] Gomathy, Dr CK, and Dr V. Geetha. "Voice based University Information Chatbot System." International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology E-ISSN (2021): 2395-0056.
- [10] Prasad, V. Akshatha, and R. Ranjith. "Intelligent chatbot for lab security and automation." 2020 11th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT). IEEE, 2020.